

RESCUER

Showing the way to the future of Emergency Responders

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SIGNALS

COLLECTION

- Enhanced hearing
- Robust vision in adverse conditions
- Augmented olfaction
- Remote touch
- Radar sensing

TRANSDUCTION

- Augmented sense collection and transduction
- Smart sensing framework

PROCESSING

- Situation-aware information prioritization
- Cognitive load balancing
- Biosignals monitoring

COMMUNICATION

- Ad hoc FRs communication
- Seamless communication with Command & control

PERCEPTION

- Augmented reality interfaces
- Long term monitoring of exposure to hazardous environment
- Black box for buildings

- Perception of wireless devices for victim localization

- Signs of life detection
- Visual based self-localization
- Inertial based localization
- Galileo- assisted localization

@H2020Rescuer
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PARTNERS:

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